

**TO ENHANCE STUDENTS PLACE IN NATURE BY FORMING A
POSITIVE PERSONAL ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE ENVIRONMENT.**

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ABSTRACT In this article, the issue that is considered urgent in modern times, that is, to provide environmental education by protecting and respecting nature, and by forming a positive personal attitude to the environment, to organize education and training to increase students' place in nature. is talked about.

KEY WORDS: Ecological problems, ecological education, ecological education, ecological outlook, environment, atmospheric air, public health, nature protection.

INTRODUCTION By the present time, the deterioration of the ecological situation on the planet Earth, i.e. the pollution of soil, air and water with various wastes and harmful substances, the reduction and destruction of useful species of plants and animals, grasslands, orchards and mountain slopes It is happening as a result of situations such as excessive use of bushes, trees and mineral resources. In order to study these problems, first of all, it is necessary to teach students to deeply understand the changes in nature, identify the causes of environmental problems in nature, take a positive approach to correcting negative situations, not only take into account the laws of nature, but also based on these it is important to educate people who organize their activities. Therefore, in these lessons, the teacher teaches students to protect the environment, to teach children the rules of behavior in nature, to show respect for it. In the opinion of E.S.Hoshimova: "In the formation of an active ecological position, the interconnection of the fields of education in this direction is of great importance. In this process, ecological education does not consist only in the formation of theoretical views on nature, but also involves the formation of faith and preparation for practical activities. First of all, it is important to inform students about the negative impact of various plants, factories, and chemical enterprises on nature and various objects of the environment. All the work carried out in the general education system of our country on nature protection is aimed at one main goal - to educate the young generation responsibly in the

situation of the natural environment and its rational use. That is why today's school teachers have the task of forming an attitude towards nature and ecological consciousness among schoolchildren of a younger age, focused on the absence of contradictions between man and nature. The main task of such education is to form a positive personal attitude to the environment in students, as well as to increase the child's place in nature and its role in its preservation. That is why methodical work, expanding the scope of scientific research in this field, developing methodical manuals and recommendations for teachers are important in ensuring the quality of environmental education. Education in the "broad sense" is an objective process, a social process that takes place in society without depending on will. Education in the "narrow sense" is a conscious and planned influence on a child by adults or a special social institution. It is especially important to teach students to protect nature on the basis of creating a new generation of integrative programs from ecology in the continuous education system. That's why Ye.B. Aydarov, "Students are given the opportunity to use actions based on a certain system in order to meet today's requirements in the following way:

firstly, about environmental education - providing complete information;
secondly, providing information about values and dividing them into themes;
thirdly, to clarify the essence of a certain topic;
fourth, to collect information that illuminates the spiritual aspects of national values;
fifthly, it is required to bring national-spiritual values into a whole system.

CONCLUSION In our opinion, in the process of studying ecology, teachers should have a good knowledge of the causes of natural phenomena, the relationship of objects to each other, and the disturbance of the balance between nature and man. That is, on the basis of improving their culture of positive attitude towards the environment, it is necessary to strictly master and observe the laws of nature, and to create conditions for the formation of a careful moral attitude towards ecology.

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